

DAMAGE DETECTION IN HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANELS BY ACTIVE THERMOGRAPHY

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Objective

In this study, honeycomb sandwich panels consisting of highly fire retardant phenolic resin and Nomex™ core designed for application in an aircraft cabin interior are investigated by LT and PT techniques. To do so, three different artificial damage modes are created in phenolic resin/glass fiber/ Nomex™ honeycomb composites by integration of oil into the honeycomb cells to simulate the liquid ingress, placing a Teflon film between core and face sheet during the manufacturing to create debonding, and using out-of-plane bending of composites to form delamination. PT and LT are successfully applied to characterize three different damage types in details.

Introduction

Phenolic resin/Glass fiber/ Nomex™ Sandwich Structure

- Low heat release
- Highly fire retardant
- Highly used in aircraft, ship and railway interiors

What are the most common defects?

How can they be detected?

Infrared Thermography

❖ Lock-in thermography (LT) and pulse thermography (PT) are the most preferred ones in the field of NDT due to their rapid detection, in-service applicability and being non-contact.

Why Thermography?

- Being non-contact
- Rapid scanning
- Portable
- In-service applicability
- Ability to inspect large area

Experimental

- 1) Preparing the Glass Fibre Reinforced Phenolic Prepreg
- 2) Curing under a hot press at 120°C

3 artificial defects created during/after manufacturing for detection

1st Defect

Embedding paraffin oil in cells before curing

2nd Defect

Placing Teflon film during manufacturing to perform debonding

3rd Defect

Using out-of-plane bending of sandwich structures to form delamination

Results

$$\mu = \sqrt{\frac{2\alpha}{\omega}} = \sqrt{\frac{\alpha}{\pi f}} \text{ and } z = r_1 \mu$$

Thermal Diffusion Length (TDL)

Frequency of Heat Source (Hz)	Depth of Defect (mm)
0.1	1.4163
0.07	1.6928
0.05	2.0029
0.04	2.2393
0.02	3.1669
0.01	4.4787
0.002	10.0147

Estimated DTL depth of defect at given frequency in LT

✓ The lower the frequency, the deeper the depth

Conclusion

A honeycomb sandwich composite structures with various damage types were inspected by LT and PT techniques. Both methods demonstrated the capability to detect various damages in the structure. In particular;

- In the liquid ingress test, although PT is fast and easy to use, LT provides clearer and sharper visualization image since controlled energy stored on the surface of specimen, and heat can penetrate deeper sinusoidally in LT.
- In debonding test, Teflon film between the face sheet and the core, despite high speed of PT method, LT method provides us with more accurate and clearer information on the damage state of debonding.
- In the delaminated sample, the LT method provides a more accurate view of the boundaries of damage and provides a higher sensibility to detect the depth of damage compared to PT. In particular, only LT method was able to detect the delaminated region after out-of-plane bending since LT has an advantage of examining thick sample if lower frequency (e.g. 0.002 Hz) is given.

This study demonstrates that the deeper view on how LT and PT can be correlate to the different damage types and different damage depths.

References

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